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Identity and Consent Management for EU Digital and Data Strategies

Empowering data ownership in the EU

CONSENTIS is geared to alleviate the challenges posed by personal data sharing towards the implementation of EU regulations and strategic initiatives like eIDAS, EU Data Spaces and GDPR. It introduces a novel framework which offers Self-Sovereign Identity and user-centric consent management solutions that enable users to:

- Have full control over their personal data collection and usage.
- Provide informed consent through user-friendly interfaces and notifications.

“THE PROPOSED FRAMEWORK IS AGNOSTIC TO EXISTING SERVICES AND FORMATS AND GUARANTEES HIGH LEVELS OF PROTECTION AVOIDING POTENTIAL LEGAL UNCERTAINTY, THROUGH A CONTINUOUS ASSESSMENT MECHANISM FOR SECURITY, RISK AND LEGAL ASPECTS.”

CONSENTIS use cases

The project is all about empowering individuals to take charge of their personal data. By implementing cutting-edge technologies, it aims to optimize identity verification, improve data management, and enable secure, consent driven sharing of personal information. During the project’s lifecycle, three real-world use cases will be executed to highlight how the framework can strengthen privacy, security and give individuals control over their data.

CONSENTIS concept

Objectives

1. Developing a framework that allows individuals to keep control of their personal data.
2. Ensuring compliance with EU regulations.
3. Integrating Privacy-Preserving Technologies to ensure secure and transparent data transactions.
4. Validating developed solutions through real-world scenarios.
5. Connecting with external stakeholders to promote project results.

In Use Case 1: led by NDP, a digital health app lets users submit their symptoms and securely share them with doctors, stored in a national healthcare registry. The app monitors ongoing data, notifies the user, and generated consent policy.

In Use Case 2: a user applies for life insurance and Karavias insurance company requests specific information from a hospital based on the user’s location. CONSENTIS lets users approve or reject consent and choose which hospitals will share their data ensuring alignment with their preferences

In Use Case 3: Karavias insurance company requests healthcare data for analytics. The national healthcare system checks user consent first. If a user hasn’t already provided consent, they are notified and can update their preferences. If consent is denied, PET technologies are used to create compliant datasets for protecting individual privacy.

| 1st plenary meeting in Braunschweig

On November 6-7, 2024, the 1st plenary meeting of CONSENTIS was successfully held in Braunschweig, hosted by our partner AEGIS. Representatives from all partners participated, engaging in in-depth discussions on crucial project aspects. The event provided a valuable opportunity for collaboration, aligning strategies, and refining project objectives. The meeting also featured a social gathering, fostering stronger relationships within the consortium.

| A multidisciplinary collaboration

Academic and research institutions contribute with expertise in privacy-preserving technologies, identity management, and user-centric design. Industry partners focus on the technical development, integration, and scalability of the solutions. Legal and ethical experts help navigate compliance with GDPR and other privacy regulations, ensuring the project adheres to the highest standards of data protection.

| Women driving Innovation in CONSENTIS

We are committed to fostering gender equality and ensuring diverse representation at all project levels. With key partners such as TIU and FundISYS led by accomplished female scientists, we continue to highlight and support women's leadership in digital security and innovation. Inclusivity and diversity drive our mission to build more equitable and accessible technological solutions.

| Next face-to-face meeting

The 1st General Assembly Meeting will take place in Patras on March 18-19, 2025. The meeting will focus on activities carried out under the Work Package 2, titled "User Requirements". UPAT, as the leader of this Work Package, will host the event on its premises.

NEXT PLENARY MEETING

TO BE HELD 18-19 MARCH 2025

IN PATRAS GREECE

HOSTED BY UNIVERSITY OF PATRAS

JOIN US IN SHAPING THE FUTURE OF DIGITAL IDENTITY!

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